

Studies on Some Less Familiar Ferrocyanogen Complexes. Part X. Composition of Molybdenum(VI)- Ferrocyanide Complex

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The interaction of Mo(VI) and K_4FeCy_6 results in the formation of both soluble and insoluble ~~complexes~~ depending on the concentration and pH of the reactants. The composition of the complex has been determined from potentiometry, conductometry, spectrophotometry, and by analysis. All the methods show the formation of the complex $(MoO_4)_2FeCy_6$.

Preliminary experiments on the interaction of Mo(VI) and K_4FeCy_6 had revealed the following interesting aspects of the reaction:

(i) Dark brown precipitate is obtained on mixing the ordinary dilute solution ($\approx 0.1M$) in the highly acidic range.

(ii) With dilute solution of the reactants ($10^{-3}M$), a soluble, reddish brown complex (most probably a colloidal solution) is obtained.

(iii) With dilute solutions in the pH range beyond 3.8 (4.0 to 5.2) a soluble, reddish brown complex is obtained.

(iv) Fairly concentrated solution of the reactants ($0.5M$) forms a highly viscous colloidal solution (showing great tendency for gelation)¹.

In view of the above complexities inherent in this reaction, it was thought worthwhile to carry out comprehensive study on its different aspects. The present communication deals with the composition of the complex (both in its apparently soluble and precipitate) employing different physico-chemical methods.

The precipitate obtained by the interaction of Mo(VI) sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide was also analysed in order to confirm the results of instrumental methods,

EXPERIMENTAL

A solution of potassium ferrocyanide was prepared as described earlier². For physico-chemical studies, a solution of Mo(VI) was prepared by dissolving a known amount of A. R. molybdic acid in HCl (A. R) and its strength was determined gravimetrically³;

¹ Malik *et al.*, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1962, **32A**, 129.

² Haque and Malik, *this Journal*, 1962, **39**, 356.

³ Pani and Rao, *Oorr. Sci.*, 1953, **22**, 237.

for chemical analysis Mo(VI) was prepared by dissolving a known amount of $\text{MoO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in warm H_2SO_4 (conc.).

Formation and Composition of the Complex.—To the solution of molybdenum (VI) the potassium ferrocyanide was added; the brown precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with water till free of sulphate and ferrocyanide ions, and dried (CaCl_2). Iron and molybdenum in the precipitate were estimated after peroxide fusion as Fe_2O_3 and PbMoO_4 respectively. Cyanogen was estimated after distillation of the precipitate with H_2SO_4 and titration of the distillate (HCN) with AgNO_3 solution making due allowance for the formation of ammonium salts during distillation. The results of analysis are summarised below.

Constituent.	Percentage.	Equiv.	Ratio.
MoO_2	57	0.4420	2.0
Fe	12	0.2148	1.0
CN	30	1.1538	5.6

The composition of the complex may be written as $(\text{MoO}_2)_2 \text{FeCy}_6$.

Titrations.—Conductometric and potentiometric titrations were performed as described earlier². The results are summarised in the following tables.

TABLE I

Direct potentiometric titrations.

K_4FeCy_6 in the cell.		Vol. of 0.1M Mo(VI)	Combining ratio
Vol.	Conc.	from the curve.	Mo(VI) : FeCy_6^{4-} from the inflection point.
20 ml	$4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$	16.0 ml	2.0 : 1
20	2.0×10^{-2}	8.0	2.0 : 1
20	1.0×10^{-2}	4.0	2.1 : 1

TABLE II

Reverse potentiometric titrations.

Mo (VI) in the cell.		Vol. of 0.1M- K_4FeCy_6	Combining ratio
Vol.	Conc.	from the curve.	Mo (VI) : FeCy_6^{4-} from the inflection point.
20 ml	$4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$	3.8 ml	2.1 : 1
20	2.0×10^{-2}	1.9	2.1 : 1
20	1.0×10^{-2}	1.0	2.0 : 1

TABLE III

Direct conductometric titrations.

Vol. and conc. of K_4FeCy_6 in the cell.	Vol. of 0.1M Mo(VI) from the curve.	Combining ratio Mo(VI) : $K_4FeCy_6^{4-}$ from inflection point.
40 ml $2.50 \times 10^{-3} M$	1.00 ml; 2.00 ml	1. : 1 and 2.0 : 1
40 1.66×10^{-3}	0.76 ; 1.50	1.1 : 1 and 2.2 : 1
40 1.25×10^{-3}	0.54 ; 1.00	1.08 : 1 and 2.0 : 1

Reverse conductometric titrations [Mo(VI) in the cell] could not be carried out due to high conductance of Mo(VI) solution.

Absorption Study

The absorption studies on the soluble complex (obtained by mixing highly diluted solutions of the reactants) were made with Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20. Job's method of continued variation⁴ was employed for determining its composition. Since the absorption values in the case of solutions containing colloidal aggregates (as probable here) might not be very reliable, the results of Job's method were verified by using the slope-ratio method⁵.

For Job's method, two concentrations of the Mo(VI) (2.0×10^{-3} and $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) were used and nine mixtures containing 1 to 9ml of Mo(VI) and 9 to 1 ml of K_4FeCy_6 were prepared in pyrex boiling tubes. Measurements were made in the wave length range 450 to 600 μ . On plotting the optical density values (the absorption of the reactants being negligible) at different wave lengths, peaks were, however, obtained at the same ratio [Mo(VI) : $FeCy_6^{4-} = 2:1$] indicating the formation of only one complex. The result is shown in Fig. 1. A maximum at the same ratio was found for a different concentration of the reactants ($2 \times 10^{-3} M$).

For the slope-ratio method, in one set a fixed amount of K_4FeCy_6 (5ml, $2 \times 10^{-3} M$) was taken and varying amounts of Mo(VI) (0.2, 0.4, 1.8, 2.0 ml) were added; in the other set, the reactants were mixed in just the other way.

DISCUSSION

Potentiometric titrations between Mo(VI) and potassium ferrocyanide provide a combining ratio of 2:1, pointing towards formation of the complex $(MoO_2)_2 FeCy_6$. The reactions may be represented as:

followed by

The conductometric titrations also provide the same results [it shows the formation of one m:fe complex in the ratio 1:1 of composition $K_2(MoO_2)FeCy_6$] although sharp

4. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, *x*, 9, 113.

5. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4448.

breaks are not obtained due to formation of the colloidal aggregates during the reaction. It is rather interesting to note that Pani and Rao³, on the basis of conductometric titrations, showed the existence of a similar complex in the precipitation reaction between molybdic acid and potassium ferrocyanide.

FIG. 1

Reactants : $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Job's method of continued variation supplied a very reliable information about the formation of the complexes in the molar ratio of 1:1. The method has also its limitations when applied to colloidal aggregates. But many authors^{4,5} have successfully employed it in cases where the molar ratio is 1:2 or even 1:3, 4, 5. Recently the author⁶ also employed the method successfully in studying colloidal solutions of chromic ferro- and ferricyanides. In the present investigation, peak occurs at the molar ratio 2:1 (Fig. 1). From these results it may be concluded that a complex of the type $(MoO_2)_2 FeCy_6$ is formed.

6. Ang and Green, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 5486.7. Dey and Banerji, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 134.8. Malik, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18B, 463.

Confirmation of the above results was made on the basis of the slope-ratio method⁵. The ratio between the slopes (by taking one reactant in excess and varying the other *vice versa*) providing a molar ratio of 2:1 indicates that the reaction takes place by two moles of Mo(VI) and one mole of K_4FeCy_6 .

Finally, the results obtained by chemical analysis are also in agreement with those obtained from potentiometric, conductometric, and spectrophotometric methods. The slightly low value of cyanogen may be ascribed to experimental error.

Further work on obtaining $(MoO_4)SO_4$ in the white crystalline form and its reaction with K_4FeCy_6 under different pH and concentrations is in progress.

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